

INDIANS IN UNITED ARAB EMIRATES

Muhammad Azhar

Chairman and Senior Professor, Department of West Asian and North African Studies
Faculty of International Studies
Aligarh Muslim University
Email: azharmuh@gmail.com

Abstract:

The phenomenon of Indians going to work in the countries of Gulf Cooperation Council is not a new phenomenon. It continues since ancient times. However, the rapid expansion of this phenomenon has been a trend in the oil era. It is reported that Indians in G.C.C countries are over 9 million. In UAE alone, it is found that Indians are over 4.3 million. Thus, UAE has been a very important destination for Indian employment seekers. It can boast of having largest concentration of Indian passport holders outside India. Indians are the largest chunk of expatriate workers. The stamp of Indian expatriate workers is evident in all sectors of the economy of UAE. As Indians are present in all the economic sectors of UAE. Many Indians have progressed phenomenally in UAE and constitute an important factor in UAE's journey to the present level of development. These Indian workers have been an important source of remittance earnings. UAE has been the largest source of earning for India as it surpasses all countries of the world including USA and Saudi Arabia in sending remittance inflows to India. Indians in UAE have been facing many problems which have been discussed in detail in the paper. The onslaught of Covid resulted in a kind of disruption to the outflow of Indian expatriate workers to UAE. However, it was overcome quickly. And number of Indians in UAE surpassed all previous records. In the meantime, India and UAE arrived at Comprehensive Economic Partnership Agreement (CEPA). This also has some reference to the Indian expatriate workers. This paper examines in detail the various aspects associated with the phenomenon of Indians migrating to United Arab Emirates for the purpose of employment. It also provides several recommendations based on the findings of indepth research on this phenomenon.

Keyword: Remittances, Kafala, wages, population, CEPA, skilled, unskilled.

Introduction

The economy of the United Arab Emirates has been dominated by oil and gas. The prosperity and progress that is observed in UAE has been due to the revenues inflow on account of oil and gas exports. Prior to the discovery of oil, Pearl fishing and agriculture had been the mainstay of economy of the region which now constitutes this country. It was simple and primitive. Pearl fishing was the chief fishing source of its national wealth. (Al-otaiba, 1977). Although the land of UAE has been mainly dessert but some regions in UAE, the soil was fertile and water was available for agriculture (Bowen, 1980). In those days, people in the trucional states that constitute the present United Arab Emirates produced only what they needed. It was a subsistence economy. The discovery of oil in Abu Dhabi and Dubai resulted in unification of these trucional states as United Arab Emirates in 1971. (Zakaria, 2018) Oil was discovered in commercial quantities in 1958 in Abu Dhabi, in 1966 in Dubai and in 1972 in Sharjah. (Al-otaiba, 1977). Further, with the onset of oil era, petroleum and natural gas became the mainstay of the economy of United Arab Emirates.

Each federation members of United Arab Emirates has considerable autonomy over their economic and financial affairs. This has enabled the federation members to pursue their own preferred economic policies. Abu Dhabi with about 90% of UAE's total oil reserves pursued on developments based on its energy resources. Other emirates members have pursued their own type of development strategy as their oil reserves are very limited. Dubai has become a global trade centre. Other members have pursued their unique economic policies. (International Monetary Fund 2002) The largest of these Emirates, Abu Dhabi has invested heavily in Dubai and other emirates. The establishment of 'free zones' in all of the emirates of UAE has been to become an international business hub. It was reported that there were 47 special economic zones (SEZs) in United Arab Emirates (Al Mutawa, 2022). These zones have been providing substantial fiscal incentives, cost and custom benefits, vast business opportunities and world class infrastructure. These SEZs have been able to attract significant FDI and skilled manpower. They have special contribution in the economic development of United Arab Emirates. (Al-Mutawa, 2022). United Arab Emirates has also established itself as a financial hub in the region, attracting international banks, investment firms and insurance companies. The economic development in UAE is also boosted by its active sovereign wealth funds (Arabian Business, 2002). The discovery and export of oil changed the economy

and society drastically. Based on the massive inflow of oil revenues, United Arab Emirates also followed in the footsteps of neighbouring oil exporting Gulf countries. The country provides a welfare system taking care of its citizens from cradle to grave. UAE provides free education, subsidized housing, guaranteed public sector employment and free medical care to its citizens. (Hatherby-Greene, Peter, 2018). The G.C.C countries including United Arab Emirates have been following liberal tax regime. Till date there are no direct and personal tax in UAE as well as other G.C.C countries (Ezenagu, 2021). The non existence of direct taxes as well as even indirect taxes in UAE had been a very important incentive for the expatriate workers including Indians to aspire for employment opportunities in United Arab Emirates. It must be mentioned that value added tax has been introduced in United Arab Emirates in 2018 only. (Gulf News, 2023) . However, this has been much below the global VAT rate. Thus the current tax regime prevailing in UAE is still not a major prohibitive factor for expatriates of all countries to seek employment in United Arab Emirates. And this country remains attractive for the expatriate workers.

Population in UAE

The information about the population in United Arab Emirates is provided in table 1. The data is provided for the period 2010-2024. It starts from end of the first decade to the recent times. The population in United Arab Emirates increased from 8.48 million in 2010 to 10.87 6million in 2024. Thus during this period, the population in UAE increased by about 28.0 percent during this period. From the table it is evident that the population in UAE is very much skewed in favour of males. During 2010 the female proportion in UAE population was estimated at 27.2 percent. However the female proportion in UAE population increased to 36.0 percent in 2024. This skewed gender population against female is attributed to the dominance of expatriates in population. It should be noted that not all expatriates keep their family with them in UAE. Although they have been working in UAE for a long time but keeping their families in their countries. (Debel Air, 2018). In fact the substantial growth in UAE population is explained by high influx of expatriate workers in UAE. And as majority of the expatriate workers do stay in UAE without their families and it reflects the asymmetric gender ratio in UAE. It is also found that the share of expatriates in UAE population has been increasing steadily. The proportion of expatriates in UAE population is provided in table-2. The share of nationals and non-nationals in UAE population has

been provided in this table. During 2001, the share of non nationals in population of UAE was estimated to be between 80-85 percent. Where as nationals constituted only 15-20 percent. By 2010, the share of non nationals increased to 88.5 percent and nationals reduced to 11.5 percent in UAE's total population. And this is maintained till now. From 2010 to 2025, the share of non-nationals and nationals in UAE's total population has been steady at 88.5 percent and 11.5 percent respectively. The dominance of expatriates in UAE population is clearly evident from the previous discussions. Once the expatriate domination in UAE population is established, the ensuing discussion would concentrate on country wise population of expatriates in United Arab Emirates. The data about the country wise population of expatriates in United Arab Emirates has been provided in table 3. The data is for 2024. It is found that Indians constitute the largest chunk of not only the expatriate population but total UAE population. It is found that 38 percent of total UAE population consists of expatriates from India. Thus Indians constitute the largest contingent of expatriate workers in UAE. Further, UAE can be designated as a country where the largest number of Indian passport holders are concentrated. (Ministry of External affairs, 2024). The second largest contingent of expatriate worker in United Arab Emirates comes from Pakistan, who constitute over 16 percent of total UAE population in 2024. Expatriates from Bangladesh are third largest among expatriates in UAE, making 7.38 percent of its total population. Expatriate from Iran and Egypt each constitute over four percent of UAE's total population. Whereas expatriates from Sri Lanka and China each constitute over 2 percent of UAE's population. If we add the expatriates from India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka and Nepal it comes to 68.36 percent of UAE's total population. Hence it can be concluded that the expatriate workers from South Asian countries not only constitute majority in UAE's labour market but also in its total population. (T.Malit Jr, Froilan and Al Youha, Ali, 2013). The expatriate workers from the south Asian countries who are exporters of manpower to the gulf countries including United Arab Emirates constitute the backbone of the UAE economy. The expatriate workers including Indians are essential component of the development in Gulf countries.(Raja and Oomen, 2020)

Indians in UAE

Indians particularly those from coastal regions have been travelling to UAE and neighbouring countries since time immemorial. They had been going to United Arab Emirates for business and other activities. The data

provided by Ministry of External Affairs gives the data about persons of Indian origin (PIOs) in United Arab Emirates at 5,269 (MEA 2004). The persons of Indian origin are those people who are citizens of their host countries where their forefathers had emigrated to these countries many generations ago. For example, the al-Ghurair family is one of most influential business families in UAE whose origin is traced to Indian state of Gujarat. Juma Al Majid is founder of the Juma Al Majid Group. The family is well respected in UAE civil society and is a significant player in construction, automotive and financial services. Their roots are also traced back to India. Other families like Al-Fardan, Al-Moosa, Al-Rais and Al-Ansari have Indian ties. (Ausaf, 2024)

Further, in United Arab Emirates there are several families living for generations, there is also vast population of second or third generation UAE born Indians. They share the typical UAE culture formed by the interaction with UAE people and people coming from all the parts of the world. Successful Indians include entrepreneurs who have established national franchises such as Lulu Hypermarkets, Jashanmal group, Ajmal perfumes, Amber packaging industries, Jumbo electronics, Choithrams, Varkey group, Alukkas and New Medical centre. The Dubai based Indians millionaires include Micky Jagtiani of the Landmark group, Yusuf ali M.A of EMKE group, Ravi Pillai of the Ravi Pillai group, the Chabria family of the Jumbo group, The Sunny Varkey group of GEMS Education, Tony Jashanmal of the Jashanmal group and Joy Alukas of Joy Alukas Jewellery. A Merrill Lynch report estimated that there were approximately 33,000 Indian millionaires staying in United Arab Emirates (Merrill Lynch, 2025). Further, it was reported that the number of Indian millionaires in UAE saw an 85 percent growth between 2013 and 2023. Thus a substantial proportion of the Indian expatriate workers in UAE have done exceptionally well. The number of Indian expatriate workers in United Arab Emirates from 1975 to 2024 is provided in table 4. As already mentioned, Indians have been present in the region but the phenomenon of large scale inflow of Indian and other expatriates to United Arab Emirates began in the Nineteen seventies with the massive inflow of oil revenues to UAE and the region. Thus by 1975, the Indian expatriates worker to UAE rose to approximately 1,70,500. This rose to 2,50,000 by 1983 and 4,00,000 by 1991. Indian expatriate workers in 2001 increased to 900,000. By 2010, it doubled to 18,00,000. Further, by 2015 Indians expatriate in UAE had increased to 2,60,0000. The

presence of Indian expatriate in 2020 had further increased to 3,420,000. And finally by 2024 Indian expatriates in UAE were reported at 4.3 million. Thus during the five decades of oil era, the population of Indian expatriates in United Arab Emirates grew from 170,500 in 1975 to 4,300,000 in 2024. Thus growing by about 25 times. The expatriate from Kerala constitute the largest segment of Indians in UAE, followed by Tamil Nadu and Andhra Pradesh. However, in recent years expatriates from the north Indian states have also joined Indian expatriates in United Arab Emirates in large numbers. The approximate break-up of Indian expatriate workers in UAE is that 65 percent of Indian expatriate workers belong to the blue-collar category. That is they are employed mostly in construction companies, municipalities, agricultural farms and domestic sector. Where as 20 percent of the Indian expatriates belong to the white collar category. That is they are employed as clerical staff, shop assistants, salesman and accountants e.t.c.. The remaining 15 percent of Indians in U.A.E. are professionals and businessmen. They are doctors, engineers, chartered accountants, Managers and often highly paid professionals. (Embassy of India, 2024). The Indian expatriates in UAE are largely responsible for building and staffing the UAE's physical, financial educational and health infrastructure as entrepreneurs, white and blue collar workers and labourers. This interaction between Emirates and Indians has been enabled by about two century old circulatory movement of people for the purpose of trade, employment and recreation between the Gulf's sheikhdoms and India's west Coast. This migratory movement accelerated further when Great Britain administered these emirates from 1892 to 1971 when they became independent. Mumbai (Bombay) had been a business and shopping destination for the Gulf populace for a long time.

As the oil and gas industry started taking roots in the Gulf, Indian Engineers and other required workers were given jobs. It is also reported that oil companies operating in the gulf like Anglo-Persian oil company (APOC) and Saudi ARAMCO also opened recruitment offices in Bombay in the 1950s. With the extraordinary and massive oil revenue inflow in the region including UAE, the massive outflow of workers began to UAE as well as other gulf countries. Indian professionals, blue collared workers and unskilled workers including domestic workers constitute the circulatory migratory pattern in UAE and of course other neighbouring gulf countries (Lentin, 2022). The circulatory migratory

pattern implies that expatriates never settle in these countries. They go for a particular period which is mentioned in their job contract. On completion of their contract period, they have to return back to their countries, where they have the option of getting another job contract of work in UAE or any neighbouring gulf countries. And if not then they stay back and try to absorb themselves into the local economy. Further, the data about the sector wise employment of Indian workers reveals that a vast proportion of Indians are employed in construction and manufacturing sector. The construction sector is also a major employer of semi skilled workers like electricians, plumbers, welders and heavy equipment operations. Over 35 percent of Indian workers have been engaged in manufacturing, transport and related professions. These sectors have been a major employer of Indian labour. The other major sector employing of Indian workers in the UAE has been professional and technical sectors. This sector mainly employs skilled workers such as engineers, doctors, nurses, paramedical staff, accountants, auditors, and teachers. Around 20% of Indian workers in the UAE are employed in these sectors. A large number of Indian workers are also employed in trade, restaurants, hotels, and other service industries. This sector is a major employer of salesmen, shop assistants, hotel staff, cooks, waiters, housekeepers, and other similar workers from India. Highly skilled Indian workers are also employed in the banking and real estate sectors. In addition, a small portion of the Indian workforce is employed in various personal and government services. As far as the primary sector is concerned, only a limited number of Indian workers are employed in activities such as agriculture, livestock, fishing, and mining. (Zachariah et.al, 2004)

Indian expatriate workers in the United Arab Emirates, as in other Gulf countries, are well aware that their stay in the UAE is mainly for the purpose of earning and saving money for a better future for themselves and their family members back in India. The majority of Indian expatriate workers in UAE keep their family members in India. Only those Indian expatriates who are in high salary brackets do take their families to UAE. The main aim of the Indian expatriate workers is to maximize their earning and send it back for the expenditure, savings and investment purposes. (Azhar, 2016). The estimate about the volume of remittance inflow to India from UAE is provided in table-5. The data is for the period of 2010 to 2021. From the table it is evident that the

remittance inflow from UAE to India increased by 60.4 percent. Whereas remittance from the world over increased from \$54.035 billion to \$89.375 billion during this period, thus growing by 65.4 percent. Thus, it can be said that the remittances inflow from UAE to India has grown only a bit slower than the growth in remittance inflow to India from world over. Further, it is expected that remittances from UAE would grow very fast as the fast growth in Indian expatriates in UAE during 2020 and 2024. It is also found that UAE had been the largest source of remittance inflow to India in 2021. Whereas United States and Saudi Arabia were second and third largest source of remittance inflow to India during 2021 (World Bank, 2021). The table also provides data about remittances from G.C.C. Countries and the world to India and remittance from UAE as percentage of these two. The proportion of remittances from UAE to India constituted 48.3 percent of total remittances from G.C.C countries to India in 2010. This declined to 38.2 percent in 2021. Despite a substantial increase in remittances from UAE during this period, the decline in UAE's proportion in total G.C.C remittance to India is to be explained by the rising remittance to India from Countries of Gulf cooperation council other than United Arab Emirates. As far as proportion of remittance inflow from the world is concerned it is found that it has been nearly stable during this period. This proportion declined slightly from 22.8 percent in 2010 to 22.2 percent in 2021. Remittances from Indian expatriates workers in UAE and else where have been very helpful in the proper management of balance of payments in India. It is also crucial in the management of foreign exchange.

Indians in UAE have also established a network of cultural association to cater to their requirements. Cultural associations such as India club, Indian association, Goan cultural society and many Keralite associations and other Indian associations play very important role in the cultural life of Indian expatriates in United Arab Emirates. All sections of Indian expatriate workers in UAE are very active. United Arab Emirates has a system of registering social organizations of expatriate communities to function under the rules and regulations of UAE government. It is reported that there are six registered associations in UAE. These registered associations perform the role of Umbrella bodies for smaller cultural and regional groupings. (Embassy of India, 2025). It is found that several UAE nationals understand and speak Indian languages like

Urdu and Hindi. Further, Hindi movies are very popular in UAE and also Indian music and festivals. Indian classical music, art, fashion and cuisine have made their special place in UAE (Oak, et.al., 2025)

The Indian diaspora is also very crucial element in UAE's transition beyond oil dependency towards a knowledge based economy driven by high growth sectors such as Artificial Intelligence (Dutta Gupta, 2025). The presence of several temples is reflection of the UAE's commitment to religious tolerance and multiculturalism. The first temple in UAE was built in 1958. The BAPS hindu mandir standing on 27 acres of land inaugurated in February 2024 is another signal of UAE's commitment to multiculturalism and tolerance (Oak, et.al., 2025). In a nutshell it can be observed that the Indian community has become an integral part of the economic and social structure of United Arab Emirates. In each and every sector be it trade, finance, education or health care etc. Indian's contribution in the progress of United Arab Emirates is well stamped. (Gulf news, 2025). The Indian expatriate workers are most respected for their technical competence and sense of discipline.

Prominent Indians in United Arab Emirates:

India has been among the top source of professional talent moving in to the United Arab Emirates. United Kingdom, Pakistan and United States have consecutively followed India in exporting professional talent to United Arab Emirates. In this section we shall be highlighting a few selected number of prominent Indians who have performed extraordinary and contributed to the making of the United Arab Emirates. From information technology to telephones, from schools to hospitals, the Indians have transformed and enriched the economy and society of United Arab Emirates. The first name in this context is the Jashanmal group. The company was established in Basra, Iraq in 1919. Subsequently they expanded to other gulf countries, establishing themselves in Dubai in 1956 and Abu Dhabi in 1964. The Jashanmal Group owns franchisee rights to many of world's most popular brands. Tony Jashanmal has been the executive director of the group. Under his leadership the group expanded significantly. (Zawya, 2015). The next name that comes in this list is of Mr. Sunny Varkey. Mr. Varkey is an Indian education entrepreneur and philanthropist based in Dubai. He is founder and chairman of GEMS education. This is the largest operator of private kindergarten to grade 12 schools in the world, with a network of

over 80 schools in over a dozen countries (Gulfbusiness, 2013). The next important Indian person in UAE has been Mr. Ram Buxani. Arriving in 1959, Ram Buxani had been chairman of the Cosmos ITL Group since 2014 till he expired in July 2024. International Trade Limited Cosmos Group spans UAE, Oman and India. Although textile dominates by accounting for 30 percent of Cosmos revenues, it also deals in electronics and home appliances, information technology, and hospitality. It also represents a large number of Global brands. (Gulf News, 2024).

Krishnamurthy Kumar also known as K. Kumar, had been the convener of the Indian Community welfare Committee (ICWC), a former group of dozens of Indian expatriate associations and community groups registered with Indian consulate in Dubai. Mr. Kumar was described as light at the end of tunnel for Indian expatriates in distress. He won the Pravasi Bhartiya Samman Award (PBSA) in 2008, the highest honour conferred on overseas Indians by Government of India. Under his convenership ICWC established a shelter for destitute Indian women, launched a crisis prevention programme, a legal cell and several welfare programmes for the Indian expatriates. Mr. Kumar expired in January 2025 (Gulf News, 2025). Dr. Bavaguthu Raghuram Shetty, commonly known as B.R. Shetty immigrated to United Arab Emirates in 1973 in search of better opportunities. He found the New Medical Centre in UAE in 1975. Beginning with healthcare NMC has diversified itself into financial services and also found world class pharmaceutical manufacturing unit in Abu Dhabi. In 2012 NMC health became the first UAE healthcare firm to be listed on the London Stock Exchange. However, in December 2019, a severe crash took place in NMC's share price as NMC Health was accused of inflating cash balances and concealing billions in undisclosed debt. Dr. Shetty eventually resigned from his position in February 2020. (The Times of India, 2025).

Yusufali MA has been yet another Indian expatriate who established himself as one of the foremost NRI businessmen in UAE. Yusufali came to UAE in 1973. He started with a small trading but now heads one of the biggest retail conglomerates in the world. (Gulf News, 2023).

Vidya Chabria has been leading the Dubai based Jumbo Group's global operations since 2002, after the death of her husband Manu Chabria. Manu Chabria established Jumbo Electronics as a single store in Dubai in 1974. Jumbo is a transnational conglomerate and Chabria's business

empire. The Jumbo group remains a significant entity in UAE. It is known for its retail business with brands like Sony, Dyson and Play Station. The Jumbo group operates in Japan, Hong Kong, Taiwan, Korea, and Singapore where manufacturing, sourcing and marketing takes place. The Jumbo has a controlling stake in various Indian entities also. Manu Chabria expired in 2002. (The Times of India, 2002)

Yet another Indian expatriate to build a business empire in UAE has been LT Pagarani. Having established a store in the UAE in 1974, L.T. Pagarani leads Choithrams supermarket group. It has been further diversified into hospitality, logistics and other sectors. Beyond UAE, Choithram has a presence in other GCC countries including Bahrain, Qatar and Oman. (Khaleej Times, 2018).

Micky Jagtiani is another example of the successful struggle of Indian expatriates in UAE. He created retailing giant, Landmark group in Dubai. Landmark was reported to have 2,200 stores spread across 24 countries. After his death, his wife Renuka Jagtiani is the chairwoman of Landmark group. (The Economic Times, 2024).

Yogesh Mehta is also one of the Indian expatriates who did not accept defeat. In 1990, his chemical distribution company went bankrupt in India. In 1995, he set up Petrochem in Dubai in partnership with Petrochem UK. Its distribution terminal at Jebel Ali free zone is the largest chemical distribution in the regions. Now it is fully owned by the family. (Gulf News, 2021).

These have been a sample and selective review of the extraordinary successful Indian expatriates. Such cases are in thousands. Forbes Middle East gives information about top Indian businessmen in UAE and the Arab world. Table 6 provides the recent ranking of top ten Indians in United Arab Emirates in recent year.

Problems

There is no doubt that United Arab Emirates has been an important market for seeking employment for Indians. This has already been discussed in detail. But simultaneously there have been lot of problems associated with the phenomenon which can not be ignored. The most serious problem faced by Indian expatriate workers had been the stagnation of wage rate and high inflation. Anxiety about Job safety was the next problem. Whereas anxiety about their family ranked third among the problems faced by Indian expatriate workers in UAE

(Prakash, 2014). At times Indian expatriate workers have been facing problems of non-payment, delayed payment and underpayment of wages. Harassment in the form of extra-working hours without overtime payments have also been reported. They have been working under very adverse and unsafe conditions. However, the UAE has been taking steps for labour reforms to protect the foreign workers. Further, the Kafala system has been a notorious system of exploitation of Indian as well as other expatriate workers. The Kafala system not only regulates entry and residence and also requires workers to seek permission from employers to change jobs. However, UAE has been pursuing labour reforms to protect the expatriate workers from various problems including problems arising from the Kafala system. The objective is to gradually dilute the impact of Kafala system. (Aljazeera, 2015)

As far as non-payment, delayed or underpayment of the wages are concerned, they have been numerous. However recent court rulings in UAE have very positive implications for expatriates including Indians. Recently an Abu Dhabi labour court ordered a private company to pay Dh 159,800 (\$43,540 approximately) to a long serving employee for unpaid salary and service benefits. The case was concerning an employee who worked with the same company for more than eleven years but was not paid the final salary and gratuity. It should be mentioned that under UAE labour law, employees who have served for at least one continuous year are entitled for end of service benefits. The law also requires the employees to settle all entitlements of the expatriate employee at the end of service. This and other similar decisions of UAE courts sends a strong message to the employers. (The Times of India, 2026). For smooth and systematic payment of wages, the employers have to pay wages through a government monitored payroll platform named as Wage Protection System (WPS). In case of non-compliance the company could attract punishment. WPS coverage has further expanded to include domestic and semi professional workers like private teachers, caregivers, nannies and farm technicians. (The Times of India, 2025).

It should also be noted that there is no rule for minimum wages in UAE. It is totally left to the vagaries of market forces. In the case of highly skilled workers, it may be having hardly any impact. But for jobs like housemaids, drivers, labours, workers in retail outlets and clerical staff, it has always been a factor for low wages. It should also be noted that for Visa eligibility especially family sponsorship, expatriate employees must

earn a minimum of AED 4000 per month, which is presently equivalent to rupees 99,000 (The Times of India, 2025). Further, it has been found that often Indian manpower recruiting agencies indulge in exploitation of the prospective Indian expatriate workers. Many times these agencies are reported to negotiate salary packages which have been much below the Government of India's standard. Some of these agencies have been reported to commit fraud also (Kanth, 2021). Although the Government of India has been taking steps time to time to control such brands practiced by recruiting agencies. However complaints regarding their brand keep pouring in. The problem of illegal migrants is another issue that is faced by many expatriates. Although they are termed as illegal migrants but in reality they are defaulters who have overstayed beyond their visa permit. This is not only with Indians but with expatriate workers of all nationalities. Time to time, the UAE has given general amnesty to such people without any punishment. The UAE government has been taking action against them. (Rediff, 2003). However, the most crucial problem for Indians in UAE as in other gulf countries has been their settlement, once they return back to India. The returnees need alternative employment. They require economic and social security. The Government of India has been introducing various schemes for their settlement but it remains largely ineffective (Hindustan Times, 2020).

It would also be improper not to discuss the policy of Emiratisation in UAE. This is a crucial part of UAE's vision 2030. This aims at boosting the employment of UAE citizens in skilled private sector jobs. This policy requires one percent increase, every six months in Emirati staff for skilled positions. Companies failing to meet this requirement have to face severe penalties. However, the programme also offers rewards to fully compliant companies. This approach has resulted in remarkable success in Emiratisation. (The Times of India, 2025) This has resulted in rising competition and declining opportunities for expatriate workers. Indian expatriate workers face pressures specially in sectors like insurance and finance. This would make Indian expatriate workers either to lose their jobs or to shift towards jobs which have low priority for UAE nationals.

Covid and Indian Expatriate workers in UAE

The havoc created by the Covid pandemic throughout world is well known and well documented. It created havoc in the United Arab Emirates also. Indian expatriate workers were also severally affected. Hundreds of thousands of Indians had to leave UAE because hundreds

of thousands workers were placed on unpaid leave. The Government of India operated a massive exercise named as Vande Bharat Mission to repatriate Indian Workers from UAE as well as other gulf countries. The UAE Government also took special steps to care the expatriates. UAE government, Indian Embassy and consulate and Indian Community organizations coordinated to help the Indian workers in UAE (The Economic Times 2020). Despite these steps Indian workers were hit hard in Covid. In Kerala courts were approached for landing permission for flights evacuating jobless workers from UAE. The mere scale of the Covid paralysed the healthcare and quarantine facilities all over the world. Which included India as well as the GCC countries. Indians as well as other expatriate workers suffered unimaginable mental stress and other psychological traumas. (The Straight Times, 2020). Anyway the effectiveness of the measures taken to counter the pandemic and measures to restore the confidence in the phenomenon of migration to UAE in post Covid period is quite clear. From table 4, it is found that Indians in UAE constituted 3.24 Million in 2020. This improved to 3.8 million in 2023. Whereas the number of Indians in UAE increased to 4.3 million in 2024. Thus we find an enormous growth in the number of Indians in UAE in the post Covid era. This certainly reflects the positive impact of Government of India's efforts to pave the way for the return of Indian workers back to the United Arab Emirates (The Economic Times, 2020).

India-UAE CEPA and Indian Expatriate Workers in UAE

India and United Arab Emirates arrived at the comprehensive Economic Partnership Agreement (CEPA) in 2022. (Bhattacharjee, 2022). CEPA has been followed by a Local Currency Settlement System (LCS) in 2023 to promote the use of Indian rupee and UAE Dirham for cross Border transactions. (Business Standard, 2024). It was further followed by Bilateral Investment treaty (BIT) in 2024. Both target to enhance their bilateral trade to \$200 billion by 2032 and also boost cooperation in defence, energy, space and civil nuclear sectors. (Business Standard, 2024). In addition to the above benefits, India-UAE CEPA offers benefits for the Indians aspiring to work in United Emirates also. It is understood that this would help Indian aspirants to work in UAE by easing professional mobility, opening opportunities in sectors like IT, Green technology and Artificial Intelligence etc., It was also expected to result in growth demand for Indian skilled labour in export oriented sectors like jewellery and textiles.

Further, India-UAE CEPA carries provision on mutual recognition of professional and skill-based qualifications to facilitate these workers to deliver services to both the countries (Suneja, 2023). India and UAE have also signed Mutual Recognition Agreement (MRA) for Authorized Economic Operators in 2023 itself. This agreement is expected to streamline customs procedures for professionals and facilitate easier access in healthcare, IT and engineering sectors. The India-UAE CEPA also allows for mutual recognition of professional qualifications in key fields. It is also expected to enhance the mobility of workers in engineering, accountancy and healthcare sectors (Suneja, 2023). Therefore, India UAE CEPA is bound to strengthen India's skilled labour exports to UAE. This agreement is also expected to help labour intensive Indian industries and contribute in generating large number of employment. (Ismail and Ahmad, 2024)

However, CEPA is silent on the benefits of this agreement on India's unskilled workers in UAE. And it is well known that unskilled workers dominate Indian workers in UAE as well as other Gulf countries. Thus, it is recommended that this issue should also brought under the preview of CEPA.

Conclusion:

- Indians have been present in UAE since long.
- The imprint of Indians has been evident on UAE economy even prior to the oil era.
- The inflow of oil revenues in UAE resulted in employment opportunities for Indians on a very large scale.
- At present Indians are estimated to be 4.3 million in United Arab Emirates.
- For long Indians have constituted the largest segment among expatriate workers of various nationalities in UAE.
- UAE has been a crucial place of employment for Indians.
- This is quite helpful in solving unemployment in India.
- Indians have their foot prints in all the sectors of UAE economy and contribute to the economic development of UAE.
- Indians in UAE help Indian economy strengthen by sending crucial remittances.
- A substantial number of Indians have successfully become large entrepreneurs in UAE.

Indians in United Arab Emirates – Azhar

- However, Indian expatriate workers in UAE also encounter problems that originate either in India or in UAE.
- The spread of corona created unimaginable hardships for Indians in UAE.
- However, post corona the number of Indian worker in UAE rose substantially.
- This reflects the success of Indian expatriate workers in UAE.
- The India-UAE CEPA is also concerned with the Indian skilled workers in United Arab Emirates.
- It is hoped that India-UAE CEPA, would at some stage encompass the Indian Unskilled workers also.
- It can be concluded that the prospects of Indian expatriate workers in United Arab Emirates is bright in future.

Table-1: Population in United Arab Emirates

Years	Total	Male	%	Female	%
2024	10,876,981	6,950,545	64.0	3,926,436	36.0
2023	10,483,751	6,710,892	64.0	3,772,859	36.0
2022	9,211,657	6,547,744	64.4	2,893,385	35.6
2021	9,365,145	6,512,037	69.5	2,853,108	30.5
2020	9,287,289	6,475,368	69.7	2,811,921	30.3
2019	9,211,657	6,443,813	70.0	2,767,844	30.0
2018	9,140,169	6,418,331	70.2	2,721,838	29.8
2017	9,068,296	6,392,484	70.5	2,675,811	29.5
2016	8,994,263	6,365,662	70.8	2,628,601	29.2
2015	8,916,899	6,337,454	71.1	2,579,445	28.9
2014	8,835,951	6,307,775	71.4	2,528,177	28.6
2013	8,751,847	6,276,725	71.7	2,475,122	28.3
2012	8,664,969	6,244,376	72.1	2,420,594	27.9
2011	8,575,205	6,210,600	72.4	2,364,604	27.6
2010	8,481,771	6,174,991	72.8	2,306,780	27.2

Source: data.worldbank.org

Table-2: National and non National Population in UAE (2021-25) in million

Year	Total Population (approx) millions	Non National Population (Approx %)	National population (Approx%)
2001	3.7	80-85	20-15
2005	4.66	85.0	15.0
2010	6.94	88.5	11.5
2015	8.67	88.5	11.5
2020	9.45	88.5	11.5
2024	11.03	88.5	11.5
2025	11.35	88.5	11.5

Source: Dubai Statistics Centre

Table-3: UAE Population by country of citizenship-2024

Country	Population Million	Percent of Total (%)
UAE	1.44	11.5
India	4.75	37.96
Pakistan	2.09	16.72
Bangladesh	0.92	7.38
Phillipines	0.86	6.89
Iran	0.59	04.72
Egypt	0.53	04.23
Nepal	0.39	03.15
Sri-lanka	0.39	03.15
China	0.27	02.16
All other countries	0.27	02.16
Total Expat population	11.06	88.50%
UAE: Total Population		100%

Source: United Arab Emirates (UAE) statistics, 2024
<https://www.globalmediainsight.com>

Table-4: Estimate of Indians in United Arab Emirates

Year	No of Indians in UAE
1975	170,500
1983	250,000
1991	400,000
2001	900,000
2010	1,800,000
2015	2,600,000
2016	3,554,274
2020	3,420,000
2022	3,800,000
2024	4,300,000

Source: United Arab Emirates (UAE) statistics, 2024

<https://www.globalmediainsight.com>

Table 5: Remittance inflow to India from United Arab Emirates
(Millions of US Dollars)

Year	Remittance from UAE	Remittance from G.C.C	% UAE/ GCC	Remittance from the world	% UAE/ world
2010	12,344.0	25,533.0	48.3	54,035.0	22.8
2011	14,251.0	29,694.0	48.0	63,011.0	22.6
2012	15,685.0	32,682.0	48.0	69,350.0	22.6
2013	12,563.0	36,760.0	34.2	69,970.0	18.0
2014	12,845.0	36,701.0	35.0	70,389.0	18.2
2015	13,745.0	38,578.0	35.6	68,910.0	19.9
2016	12,575.0	34,915.0	36.0	62,744.0	20.0
2017	13,823.0	38,378.0	36.0	68,968.0	20.0
2018	18,529.0	48,488.0	38.2	78,609.0	23.6
2019	18,916.0	50,300.0	37.6%	83,131.0	22.7
2021	19,800.0	51,900.0	38.2%	89,375.0	22.2

Source: Bilateral Remittance Matrix

Various years, World Bank, (www.worldbank.org)

Table-6: Top ten Indians in United Arab Emirates

Rank	Name	Designation	Organization	Industry
1	Yusuffali MA	Managing Director	Lulu Group International	Retail
2	Micky Jagtiani	Chairman	Landmark Group	Retail
3	Dr. B.R. Shetty	Managing Director/ CEO/ founder	UAE Exchange/ NMC health care	Banking and finance services/ Healthcare
4	PNC Menon	Chairman	Sabha Group	Real Estate and construction
5	Sunny Varkey	Chairman	GEMS Education	Education
6	Dr. Azad Moopen	Chairman	DM Group	Health care
7	Rizwan Sajjan	Chairman	Danube Group	Industrials
8	Syed Salahuddin	Managing Director	ETA Ascan and star group	Real Estate and construction
9	Rajen Kaliachand	Chairman and President	Dodsall Group	Real Estate and construction
10	Mohan Valrani	Sr. Vice Chairman and M.D	Al Shirawi Group	Industrials

Source: Top 100 Indian leaders, Forbes Middle East 2025, (WWW. Forbesmiddleeast.com, Accessed on 25-12-2025)

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